

Effect of Flowrate and Coolant Temperature on the Efficiency of Progressive Freeze Concentration on Simulated Wastewater

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Abstract—Freeze concentration freezes or crystallises the water molecules out as ice crystals and leaves behind a highly concentrated solution. In conventional suspension freeze concentration where ice crystals formed as a suspension in the mother liquor, separation of ice is difficult. The size of the ice crystals is still very limited which will require usage of scraped surface heat exchangers, which is very expensive and accounted for approximately 30% of the capital cost. This research is conducted using a newer method of freeze concentration, which is progressive freeze concentration. Ice crystals were formed as a layer on the designed heat exchanger surface. In this particular research, a helical structured copper crystallisation chamber was designed and fabricated. The effect of two operating conditions on the performance of the newly designed crystallisation chamber was investigated, which are circulation flowrate and coolant temperature. The performance of the design was evaluated by the effective partition constant, K , calculated from the volume and concentration of the solid and liquid phase. The system was also monitored by a data acquisition tool in order to see the temperature profile throughout the process. On completing the experimental work, it was found that higher flowrate resulted in a lower K , which translated into high efficiency. The efficiency is the highest at 1000 ml/min. It was also found that the process gives the highest efficiency at a coolant temperature of $-6\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Keywords—Freeze concentration, progressive freeze concentration, freeze wastewater treatment, ice crystals.

I. INTRODUCTION

INDUSTRIAL wastewater can contain various types of pollutant ranging from chemicals to suspended matters and the type of treatment depends on the type of the pollutants. Regardless of the type of treatment that will be applied to the wastewater, it is such an advantage if the volume of the wastewater could be reduced extensively. Reduced volume of

wastewater will result in a reduction in operation cost in terms of the utility. Hazardous wastewater is frequently treated by incineration. But to incinerate an aqueous solution, with a solid content of less than 10%, requires tremendous power to 'burn' the water and maintain the high temperature necessary to destroy the hazardous compound [1]. In addition, the combustion gas produced contributes to the emissions from the process and can rapidly exceed local limits.

In concentration of a solution, there are three methods available: reverse osmosis, evaporation and freeze concentration. Every process has their specific energy and among those three, the energy cost is the highest for evaporation (2.26kJ/g-water), intermediate for freeze concentration (0.33kJ/g-water), and the lowest for reverse osmosis because phase transition is not needed [2]. Evaporation is the simplest method which is worth the energy consumed, but it is very dangerous when hazardous volatile organic compounds (VOCs) are involved [3]. Despite of the low energy consumed in reverse osmosis, it is not a favourable method of concentration because clogging can easily occur, and the high cost involved for the osmotic pressure.

Wastewater can be treated by separating the ice crystals formed in it, because ice crystals include no components of the wastewater except water, resulting purged water being obtained [4]. This process is called freeze concentration. Freeze concentration is an operation to concentrate an aqueous solution by separating ice crystals produced in the solution [5].

Some other advantages of freeze wastewater treatment are (1) wastewater including toxic compounds [6] or heavy metals [7] can be treated which is difficult to treat biologically; and (2) a smaller facility is required compared to biological wastewater treatment [8].

There are two methods available for freeze concentration, conventional suspension freeze concentration (SFC) and progressive freeze concentration (PFC). SFC is a process of freeze concentration where the ice crystals are formed in a suspension of the mother liquor and is characterized by the generation of a size distribution of crystal growing isothermally. However, in this conventional method, the size of ice crystal is still limited [9]. The small ice crystals formed has to be transferred to a ripening vessel to be enlarged, then to a washing column and separated from the mother solution after washing with water [10]. These steps: ice nucleation, ice

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crystal growth and ice crystal separation make the whole system very expensive, which has made it unfavourable.

In compensating the disadvantages of SFC, a totally different concept of crystallization, PFC has been introduced. In this method, a large single ice crystal instead of a group of small ice crystals suspension is formed. The ice crystal is formed on the surface of the heat conducting material where the cooling is supplied. As only a single crystal is formed, its separation from the mother liquor is much easier to be handled and at a lower cost. However, despite of the easier separation, the productivity of PFC is found to be lower than the conventional SFC.

The design of the apparatus where the crystallization of ice is supposed to occur is an important factor in influencing the system efficiency. In addition, the flowrate of the solution to be concentrated and the growth speed of ice front during the freeze concentration are the two important factors that significantly influence the efficiency of the system [11]. The growth speed of ice front should be able to be controlled by the coolant temperature [2].

In this particular research a helical copper crystallization chamber was fabricated, where the crystallization of ice should take place. The newly fabricated chamber was then evaluated in terms of its efficiency according to the two parameters, which are the circulation flowrate and coolant temperature.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Materials

Glucose solutions at a concentration of 7 mg/ml were used to represent the simulated wastewater. It is very common that glucose be used in assessing the performance of a wastewater treatment system. Glucose used was 99.9% pure.

B. Equipment

Fig. 1 Diagram of the helical copper crystallization chamber (CC) structure

Fig. 1 shows the crystallization chamber (CC) fabricated using copper as the material. The thickness of the copper tube is 0.8 mm with internal diameter of 1 inch. The chamber has

three layers or stages and is also equipped with 6 stainless steel flanges where the chamber could be splitted into two. This is to enable visualization of the ice layer produced in each experiment. Nine temperature probes (thermocouples type K) were engaged in each stage for temperature profiling purpose, where the solution, copper wall and coolant temperatures are displayed by PicoLog recorder software through a connected computer.

This crystallization chamber was then immersed in a refrigerated waterbath at the desired temperatures. The coolant used was ethylene glycol at 50% volume with water.

C. Experimental Procedure

Glucose solution prepared was first kept in a freezer where the temperature of the solution should be near the freezing temperature of water. The temperature was kept at 3 to 4°C and the solution was mixed with glucose solution ice cubes to maintain the temperature during feeding.

The solution was then fed to the chamber using a peristaltic pump through a silicone tube until its full volume was filled. Each end of the silicone tube was then connected.

The filled CC was then immersed in a precooled waterbath at the desired operation temperature, while the pump was run at the desired circulation flowrate. The solution then was left for crystallization to occur for 15 minutes. After the designated time, the circulation was stopped and the chamber was taken out of the waterbath to be thawed. The concentrated solution in the silicone tube was then collected as the concentrate sample via flushing with the pump.

The flanges were unassembled and the whole volume of the concentrated solution was collected. The ice layer thickness at each flange point was measured and a sample of the ice layer produced was collected. Refractive index of each sample was then measured in order to determine its concentration.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A calibration curve for the concentration of glucose via refractive index (RI) was first constructed by making several standard solution of glucose with concentration in the range of 1 to 10mg/ml. The calibration curve is shown in Fig. 2 which agrees with previous calibration curves produced previously by other researchers [12].

Fig. 2 Calibration curve

During freezing, ice crystals were formed on the inner surface of the copper tube wall. Figs. 3 and 4 show the ice layer formed in the CC at the end of the experiments. The thickness of the layer varied with the operating conditions varied throughout the experimental works.

Fig. 3 Ice layer formed

Fig. 4 A close-up of the ice layer formed

A. Effect of Circulation Flowrate

The studied range of circulation flowrate for the newly designed PFC system was 400 to 1000 ml/min, which was chosen based on the existing pump capacity. While the circulation flowrate was varied, the other operating conditions were kept constant. Coolant temperature was kept at -8°C and the circulation period at 15 minutes.

The effect of circulation flowrate on the efficiency of the system is portrayed by the effective partition constant of the system which can be calculated through Equation (1).

$$K = C_s / C_L \quad (1)$$

where C_s is and C_L are solute concentrations in ice and solution phase, respectively [2].

The experimental value of K is measured by equation (2), where V_0 and C_0 are the volume and solute concentration at the beginning in the solution phase, respectively. V_L is the volume of concentrate produced.

$$(1-K) \log (V_L/V_0) = \log (C_0/C_L) \quad (2)$$

Fig. 5 shows the effect of circulation flowrate on the effective partition constant K .

Fig. 5 Effect of circulation flowrate on K

From the plotted graph, it can be seen that higher flowrate resulted in a lower K , which means better efficiency. This finding agrees with what was discussed earlier by Miyawaki et.al. [2] and Ramos et.al. [13], higher flowrate will result in a highly pure ice crystal layer.

Increasing the flowrate of solution promotes heat transfer with ice crystals from its tips, hence enhancing the planar ice growth from the cooling wall by keeping contaminants away from the ice-liquid interface [14]. Therefore, higher flowrate will result in ice layer with higher purity. For this system, the K value is predicted to be lower if the flowrate is further increased.

Fig. 6 shows the effect of circulation flowrate on ice purity from this study which is very similar to the previous findings.

Fig. 6 Effect of circulation flowrate on ice purity

A. Effect of Coolant Temperature

The same experimental procedure was used in order to investigate the effect of coolant temperature on the efficiency of this system. Other parameter kept constant was the circulation flowrate at 1000 ml/min and circulated for 15 minutes for crystallization.

After examining the samples and determination of its concentration, the effect of coolant temperature on K is depicted in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7 Effect of coolant temperature on K

It can be observed that lower coolant temperature resulted in higher K, which means lower efficiency for the system. At -4°C , ice layer formed was not smooth and very thin and in fact was in dendritic form. Therefore, the data collected at this temperature should not be included. Data from the temperature profiling tools shown in Fig. 8 shows that even the coolant temperature was set at -4°C , its actual temperature was only -3.1°C at average.

Fig. 8 A snapshot of the temperature profiling tool

Coolant temperature controls the ice crystal front growth rate [2]. Ice growth rate increases with increasing difference between the entering solution and the surface temperatures [15]. A decrease in the coolant temperature brings a higher growth rate of ice front, which is undesirable to produce a low K for this system. The higher the ice growth rate, the more impurities would be entrained in the ice. This is because the speed of the moving front can become too high to overtake the solute outward movement. [16] and promote solute inclusion in the ice crystals. Low growth rate gives high purity of ice produced [2].

IV. CONCLUSION

This work has proved that the designed crystallisation chamber is capable of producing ice crystals with good purity. However, those parameter studied should be further investigated in order to discover its best performance in terms

of flowrate and coolant temperature used.

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